

The integration paradox assessed: a case of cruel optimism?

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Abstract

The integration paradox denotes how immigrants who structurally integrate feel less positive towards their host societies. The concept aims to encapsulate the contradictory realities of settlers in relation to the overarching society. Even though the concept seems to achieve a multi-layered description of immigration, its theoretical and empirical construction depends on the application of a number of assumptions that rest uneasily with the supposed aims of the concept. The first concerns assumptions about society. Researchers formulate a one-way solution towards the integration paradox by depicting society as a neutral backdrop to immigrant behaviour much in line with immigration policies. Second, researchers are unclear about whether the integration paradox is a theoretical or behavioural paradox, while semantically propping up the concept towards the paradox as being behavioural. Third, researchers turn their gaze away from the complex affective strategies utilized by immigrants in favour of a problematization of a unidimensional view of their affective strategies. These practices involve a paradox: a tension between practicing unidirectional views of immigration and disavowing it. As a consequence, the integration paradox can be seen as a case of cruel optimism on behalf of the scientific endeavour. By looking closer at objectionable theorizing and empirical practices, this study paves the way for an immigration science endeavour that does justice to the complex landscape of contradictions pertinent to life as an immigrant.

Keywords: integration paradox, cruel optimism, belonging, affect

Introduction

For the past decade or so, researchers in the Netherlands and Germany have sought out to understand why a significant portion of first- and second generation immigrants perceive society in an increasingly negative manner, in particular immigrants who have structurally integrated (ten Teije et al., 2013; van Doorn et al., 2013; Verkuyten, 2016; Geurts et al., 2020). According to Wachter and Fleischmann, structural integration “entails the incorporation of immigrants into the core institutions of the host society, such as the labor market and educational system” (Wachter and Fleischmann, 2018, p. 156). When researchers found that once settlers are structurally integrated and participate in society, meaning that the process of structural integration alters them into able speakers and knowledgeable members of the workforce, it appeared that settlers become more aware of discrimination, hostility, and unequal opportunity structures. Thus, they garner a negative form of affective attachment to the society they settle in. Evidently, structural integration does not cultivate citizens into feeling positively attached to their host society so easily. They named this phenomenon the *integration paradox*.

What makes the integration paradox scientifically useful has to do with how it conceptually captures a sliver of the contradictory realities of a settler’s identity formation (Antonsich, 2010). Before coining the term, researcher commonly held the view that learning the host country’s language, obtaining higher education or participation in the labor market would lead to more intergroup contact and result in one’s psychological assimilation into their society of residence (Buijs, 2006).

This so-called ‘linear’ or ‘unidirectional’ view is that which the researchers behind the integration paradox claim to move away from (Steinmann, 2019; Esser, 2006). In other words, the integration paradox can be seen as a spate of theoretical and empirical investigations into a more complex view of the contradictions inherent to the affective experiences of migrants. In general, it can be said that it is desirable to move away from classical functionalist views of structural integration towards examining how integration is made up out of a constellation of processes.

In this paper, we set out to assess the theoretical apparatus underscoring the integration paradox. We show that the integration paradox is theoretically and empirically objectionable for posing as a turn towards a multi-layered understanding of integration while it still holds root in a functionalist and unidirectional perspective of integration. As a result, the concept rests uneasily with the commitment to better understand the real contradictions and complexities behind a migrant’s affective attachment within the process of structural integration. By showing these uneasy commitments in this contribution, we aim to open the question about whether the current theoretical approaches to understanding the integration paradox are desirable.

The line of empirical research that we put into question encapsulate more than a decade of claims about turning away from classical understandings of integration. For this paper, we critically review studies by van Doorn et al., Tuppatt and Gerhards, van Maaren and van de Rijt, Geurts et al., Verkuyten, De Vroome et al., ten Teije et al., and Steinman (de Vroome, 2013; ten Teije et al., 2013; van Doorn et al., 2013; Verkuyten, 2016; Steinmann, 2019; Geurts et al., 2020; Tuppatt and Gerhards, 2020; van Maaren and van de Rijt, 2020).

The studies in question are part of a long-standing empirical discussion on the precise mechanisms that drive the phenomenon at hand. Although the conceptual apparatus underscoring integration paradox seems to be generally accepted by most scholars, there are a few exceptions or special cases wherein no evidence could be found for specific measures and settings (van Maaren and van de Rijt, 2020).

In contrast, we observe that theoretical work has not gone beyond a set of comparable theories. These theory selection practices assert that little discussion is needed about the assumed conceptual relations adhered to in empirical practice. The exception to the rule are two noteworthy papers, which we will treat near the end (Eijberts and Ghorashi, 2017; Pozzo and Nerghes, 2020). Given this lack of rigorous theorizing, we ask, what are the premises under which researchers justify the conceptual apparatus central to the integration paradox? How does the conceptual apparatus central to the integration paradox insinuate empirical beliefs about the affective constituency of structural integration?

This study starts with an examination of the theoretical building blocks fundamental to the integration paradox: the individual and society. We investigate the assumptions pertinent to these fundamental building blocks throughout the first three sections. In the first section we show that despite best intentions, it is the case that the integration paradox is objectionable on the grounds that the term garners its validity from a conflation with political (non-epistemic) and scientific (epistemic) purposes. In section two, we discuss the problem of ‘one-wayness’ inherent to how the integration paradox is formulated. In section three, we show that the concept’s theoretical apparatus semantically props up a simplified view of the contradictions inherent to a migrant’s life. Then, we tease out how, given the aforementioned criticisms, researchers also problematize migrant behaviour where there is no need to do so, and that researchers frame their research towards possible solutions that benefit neither society nor the migrant. In the fourth section, we argue that given the three aforementioned criticisms, the integration paradox might be best understood as imposing a ‘cruel optimism’ on both society and the individual immigrant. Cruel optimism is, according to Berlant, a relation in which “something you desire is actually an obstacle to your flourishing” (Berlant, 2011, p. 1). This concept will prove especially useful in reframing the integration paradox towards more epistemically justified avenues. Finally, we conclude this paper by suggesting alternative routes to a more refined understanding of affective attachment during the process of structural integration.

A review of the dominant theories

We shall not argue against the idea that first- and second-generation migrants feel much less belonging to the country as a result of structural integration. Rather, we argue against the assumptions that researchers hold to buttress empirical findings. Getting there requires us to first tease out what these theories are all about. We therefore start this section by scrutinizing the theories selected by researchers on the basis that they are warranted alternatives to classic intergroup contact and assimilation theories.

The theory of rising expectations, relative deprivation and perceived discrimination are three of the most common theoretical explanations for negative sentiments among immigrants. These theories are the most common explanations that are tested with empirical inquiries. All three theories can be seen as extensions of one another, but it is worth dwelling on their logic if we want to understand the gap between what is claimed about society and the individual, and how they are measured.

First, the theory of rising expectations states that more educated people expect better economic opportunities. Researchers use this theory to explain the discontent or frustration that arises when higher expectations are not met by actual economic opportunities (van Doorn et al., 2013). The author uses the term ‘opportunity structure’ to denote how matters of distributive equality ‘produce different chances of being discriminated against.’ Van Doorn et al. take as an example how higher educated immigrants tend to feel like they must work twice as hard for the same reward than non-immigrants.

Secondly, the theory of relative deprivation describes that individuals or groups experience unfair disadvantages when comparing their situation to other groups or individuals. As a result, others are perceived as more advantaged, making individuals or groups feel deprived relative to the advantaged group (van Maaren and van de Rijt, 2020). As van Maaren and van de Rijt state, “higher educated immigrant adolescents may be expected to feel more relatively deprived and have, in turn, less positive feelings towards the majority than lower educated immigrant adolescents.” Ultimately, feelings of relative deprivation turn into less positive feelings towards those perceived as more advantaged.

The third theory also appeals to subjective experiences of perceived acceptance and discrimination (Lajevardi et al., 2020). Appeals to this type of explanation posit that more integrated individuals experience more discrimination because by being structurally integrated. Learning the language means having access to discriminatory discourse, both personally and nationally, turning their heightened awareness into less positive attitudes (Verkuyten, 2016).

It is useful to first explicate the fundamental building blocks of these theories – society and its relation to the individual – since they make up the conceptual apparatus of the integration paradox. This is what we set out to do in the following sections.

The first critique: an imagined community

One pattern in the literature concerns the way in which researchers invoke the value of their research with relation to what a future society should look like: an “organic totality” (Sanjinés, 2007, p. 295. This *imagined* society, one wherein citizens share feelings of “national cohesion and a shared identity”, tends to be viewed as unified and homogeneous (Geurts et al., 2020, p. 1828). In this picture, society tends to be seen as an integrated “organic totality”). One such feeling that researchers find particularly interesting is that of belonging, for belonging facilitates the flourishing of this imagined society. It is thought, by some more explicitly than others more implicitly, that a collective feeling of belonging poses as the prerequisite or even benchmark that, if upheld, generates “social cohesion” and politically an “effective democracy” (Verkuyten, 2016, p. 539; Steinmann, 2019).

Whether or not this utopian ideal is a worthwhile endeavor is irrelevant to the possible conflation between scientific knowledge and political aims. Why, we may ask, do researchers explicitly link their aspirations of an organic totality to policy concerns (Di Saint Pierre et al., 2015; Verkuyten, 2016)? Duyvendak points out that Dutch politicians “tell immigrants how to feel – above all, to feel at home in the Netherlands” as part of national strategy (Duyvendak, 2011, p. 94). His extensive review of empirical data and debates on the “right to belong and the ability to feel at home” show that promoting a sense of belonging as a matter of national unity and cohesive identity migrants with “insurmountable obstacles” (Duyvendak, 2011, p. 4, 101). More remarkable is how this essentialist view on national

identity, often linked to nationalist tendencies, is neither problematized nor suggested as an object of study. Rather, (a lack of) feelings of belonging are problematized a-priori.

Do these a-priori problematizations have a place in a scientific endeavor centered on better understanding immigration and affect? Penninx argues that conceptions of integration have wholly different functions in the scientific than the political domain (Penninx, 2019). Meaning in essence that the use of language should be studied separately in the political and scientific realm.

Against Penninx, we suggest that statements about, say, structural integration, or belonging, used in functionally different ways can still share the assumptions rooted in the same epistemology. When one states to aim for a cohesive society, we can say that the intended audience, interpretations and operationalization of that utterance can be wholly different in a research paper versus a policy document. However, the two uses of cohesive society can still be seen as two instances of the same nation-state epistemology. For how else do two statements garner warranted belief and validity in their claims? Hence, Penninx's argument about functional use as the main category of difference can be viewed as subservient to the more general argument concerning epistemology as the main category of difference.

When political meanings of belonging seep into the cracks of empirical research, epistemic and non-epistemic uses of that word become hard to distinguish. Blurrier lines between epistemic (scientific) and non-epistemic (political) interests rests uneasy with a research endeavor aimed at understanding affect in context of structural integration. Similar to Wimmer and Schiller, we surmise that this intellectual imagination of an organic totality through feelings of belonging paves the way to empirically "equate society with the nation-state, and conflate national interests with the purposes of social science" (Wimmer and Schiller, 2003, p. 576).

As a result, we observe one burgeoning problem created by this epistemological conflation between the political and scientific spheres. A researcher's reflexivity and disposition towards a socially cohesive society can prevent "research participants to develop their own meaning and positions regarding and towards categories" (Dahinden et al., 2021, p. 550). We suggest that different practices in research and policy can still be seen as differentiated in function but confounded in reflexivity. As stated in the introduction, the aim of research should be to study what is happening, garner knowledge about the actual lives of settlers, replete with paradoxes and internal and external conflicts, not to prescribe or judge what ought to happen, and dispose empirical investigations towards a desired end goal. As a first step, we conclude, the structural integration concept on which the research and analysis is based must not include (or must keep to the minimum achievable) any normative connotations on the desired end goal.

Given the lack of further theorization on this matter, it is productive to infer the categorical consequences of this lack of reflexivity. We observe that the success of structural integration then is seen as having a political dimension (how we categorize 'us' and 'them'), conflating it with an intensional dimension (how we feel towards 'us' and 'them')(Yuval-Davis, 2006). The first categorical distinction is qualified by non-paradoxical and paradoxical behaviour, respectively, while the second distinction is about acculturation as a form of positive emotional attachment. We can say that it is this sense of belonging which is implicitly treated as a criterion for deservingness for either of these categories. These differences exist in terms

composed of domestic individuals and groups ('non-immigrants'), who are already 'integrated' because of a unifying spirit, and immigrants.

Such a cohesive society, of course, has never existed and portraying it in the categorical differences ideals of cohesion generates restricts us in dealing with the increased fluidity and diversity of modern society (Crul, 2016). An example of such a restriction can be that rather than legal status as a formal citizen, feelings of belonging are operationalized as an indicator of categorically distinguishing between 'majority' and 'minority.' Interestingly, there are some parallels to the ethnic-diversity hypothesis wherein there exists a debate within the terms of intergroup contact theory on whether diversity is productive or beneficial for a number of indicators, with robust arguments prevalent in various corners (Jones et al., 2000; Glas et al., 2019; Laurence et al., 2019). In parallel, it is not ethnic diversity here but a psychometric diversity of feelings, categorized as either positive (desired) or negative (undesired), that are linked to a decline in social cohesion. Following Yuval-Davis, then, belonging is viewed as a kind of capital resource that constructs, justifies or counteracts forms of social inclusion or exclusion (Yuval-Davis, 2006).

It must be stated that we also have no pressing reason to discredit fixed and stable classifications that arise from affective or psychometric demarcations. The core of the problem here is with regards to how the distinction between 'us' and an structurally integrated 'other' rests on the imagination of Dutch society as a homogenous ethno-cultural entity. In understanding the construction of the immigrant experience, we discern a clear connection between this socio-economic notion of affect and a singular imagination of national identity wherein the latter obtains a prescriptive character. Rather than a description of an assemblage of social life in all its diversity, society could become a concept which prescribes a dominant norm of what social life should be.

The second critique: the arbitrariness of immigrant-specificity

So, we know aspirations for an 'organic totality' are much unlike society as is. Is this because of problematic immigrant behaviour, or because of the hostile attitudes to those who have become formal citizens? In between the components of this rhetorical dichotomy are a wide range of positions. For this reason, scholars often include caveats in their conclusions. For example, van Doorn et al concluded that "integration policies should not only be directed at integration among immigrants, but also at the acceptance of immigrants among the ethnic majority group" (van Doorn et al., 2013, p. 396).

Yet even if the focus would shift to the degree an ethnic majority group accepts immigrants, there remains a narrow focus on migrants in factors shaping integration processes. When focusing solely on factors related to migrants (such as their level of education and skills), the concept does not capture the multiple and systemic factors which facilitate and impede processes of affective conflict. Recognizing this shortcoming exposes the fallacy of attributing responsibility (or indeed blame) to any one party. Among the multiple factors characterizing integration processes, it is should be clear that, only some of the factors at play. Many immigrants, moreover, have family members without immigration experience, with whom processes of integration are entwined (Charsley et al., 2020).

Moreover, paying lip-service to the reference group still facilitates the objectification of the 'other.' The supposedly "troublesome phenomenon" of the integration paradox must avoid reinforcing a sense of difference and separation, of migrants set apart and problematized as in

need of integration (Verkuyten, 2016, p. 532). Its explanatory power should come from contextualising individuals within, not beyond, society, reorienting the focus of study away from migrant populations towards the population. In line with Spencer et al. here we point to a need to broaden recognition of the range of actors, and factors, involved (Spencer and Charsley, 2021). It can be said that the caveats we discussed often go along complex legitimization strategies, yet often include self-contradicting theoretical assumptions as we will show further in this section.

One example of an internal contradiction discussed within the broader research content on immigration and integration is what Klarenbeek calls ‘one-wayness’ (Klarenbeek, 2019). It mainly concerns the question as to who should adjust to whom and under what circumstances (Ager and Strang, 2008; Phillimore, 2012). To find congruence in two conflicting notions of society, integration paradox researchers put an emphasis on perceptions and feelings of individuals, rather than society, to resolve that conflict. Given this individuated focal point, a decrease in integration of the ‘organic totality’ then ceases to be a property of a social whole and becomes individualized by turning it into a property of individual people, such as settlers and their children. After all, the outcome of this tendency is that our selection of research on the integration paradox fits squarely in the assimilationist framework aimed at a cohesive society.

Given that political and scientific aims conflate within the current state of research, integration paradox research may be used to indirectly substantiate or legitimize policy choices. There is indeed a chance that non-epistemic outcomes may persist for lack of avoiding the pitfalls of one-wayness: problematizing immigrants where it is not necessary to problematize them. For example, majority members’ attitudes and behaviour are attributed a kind of instrumental value for explaining the integration paradox: rarely it is discussed how they can facilitate the integration of others – for example by banning discrimination or by adjusting institutions towards more inclusive ones – and are rarely scrutinized for *their* integration into the ideal society except for a concluding sentence or two (Verkuyten, 2016). This so-called container model of society encompasses a view that normality is contained within the majority, and deviance delegated to the minority. Such assumptions of normality and deviance have undesirable stigmatizing and marginalizing consequences.

We do not suggest that researchers continuously scrutinize their own non-epistemic impact. Rather, we emphasize that if researchers desire to understand the complexities of the immigrant experience, then framing structural integration as an obligation on behalf of the settler and not as a two-way process rest on arbitrarily distinguishing between ‘us’ and ‘them’ using the criterion of positive feelings. In the strictest sense, one can think of the average non-immigrant with a negative attitude towards the host society as showing paradoxical behaviour too. This should come as no surprise, as theories such as the theory of relative deprivation originate from an era of social justice movements, whereby the theory was a tool of understanding how people organize in social movements (Gurney and Tierney, 2021).

The third critique: a semantic propup

In this section we argue that theorizing structural integration as a one-sided affair signals a distinct “gaze of social scientists, politicians, and the engaged public”(Korteweg, 2017, p. 6, 428). The gaze turns the attention away from the complex strategies that settlers engage with in ambiguous situations and labels them collectively as paradoxical because that is the only

sensible thing to do given an assimilationist theoretical foundation. In doing so, we first discuss the oversimplification of affective attachment pertinent to the literature.

Perceptions of an external reality tend to be measured with a single question (Verkuyten, 2016; van Maaren and van de Rijt, 2020). For example, to measure the qualitative attribute of feelings of relative deprivation, researchers asked “if you compare yourself to others in the Netherlands, are your circumstances better, equal or worse off than others?” (van Doorn et al., 2013, p. 389). To give another example, feelings of perceived discrimination were measured with the following question: “how often do you feel discriminated?” (van Maaren and van de Rijt, 2020, p. 1762). Researchers aggregated these qualitative observations in quantitative form, such that they can directly observe such aggregations as frequencies (i.e., the number of times that someone feels discriminated against (1) rarely, (2) sometimes (3) and often) of occurrence.) The practice of asking single questions in combination with a one-sided vision on immigration are mutually reinforcing.

We offer two burgeoning shortcomings in how affect is measured. To begin, experiences of discrimination or feeling unwelcome concerns a wide range of responses to cope with situations that may be hostile: depression, dissociation, pragmatism, ambivalence, indifference, cynicism, or even activism. To think of attitudes as being unidimensional or bipolar results in a selective denial of attributes of attitudes. Pragmatism is not the same thing as indifference, yet both attributes might lead to someone to score at the midpoint on a bipolar scale. Someone who is ambivalent still may hold strong opinions about feeling discriminated against and perhaps even feel it more than those who readily score high but feel nevertheless conflicted.

Should the mantra of ‘negative emotions are undesired’ sweep all these phenomena under the same umbrella? If yes, then it is this simplification that leads to a hasty drive to diagnose social conflict by simplifying affect rather than better understanding the complex relations between affect and perceptions. What if we view the measurement process not as a literal measurement of, say, the quality of rarely feeling discriminated against, but as an opinion expressed in response to a survey question that is only an estimate of the *central tendency* of an individual’s attitudes or beliefs (Martinez et al., 2005)? We then run into the problem that single or even two questions are simply not enough to come to an adequate *summation* of those perceptions telling us whether they fall, overall, into any distinct attribute or another.

Furthermore, researchers tend to assign activity and passivity to the reference group or target group. One of the instantiations of this approach is discernible, both explicitly and implicitly, in the research endeavor, but most tellingly, within the conclusions drawn from the data. Geurts et al., for example,

“conclude that it is not necessarily those who have more cognitive skills who identify less with the destination country, but rather those who are structurally ‘better off.’ A direct implication hereof is that policies should not only target higher educated migrants who might disengage with the destination country, but those who are structurally more successful more generally” (Geurts et al., 2020, p. 1843).

The authors continue on those policies should especially improve in order to “attract *and retain* talented migrants in order to strengthen” the Dutch economy (Geurts et al., 2020, p. 1844). Migrants are therefore portrayed as agents who structurally integrate through purposive action. There exists a tacit differentiation between outsiders as active agents and

insiders as passive entities (Tuppat and Gerhards, 2020). This assignment of activity is further reinforced by the fact that non-immigrants and their institutional context are always perceived as a context, and nothing more except for the rare few statements. Being part of a context, both policies and members of the supposed majority as a result stand outside the process of structural integration (van Maaren and van de Rijt, 2020) despite the fact that society is far from the ‘organic totality’ such views rest on.

The following rhetorical device may illustrate how this indefinite problematization occurs within a kind of semantic framing: One can say that the antonym to (structural) integration is (structural) disintegration. That is to say, the reverse process of integrating. We have observed that, for researchers, more positive attitudes towards the host society equal further structural integration. A decrease in structural integration should then naturally equal to disintegration (Hinger and Schweitzer, 2020).

But individuals cannot disintegrate within the conceptual boundaries of the current literature because there is little paradox to be found in a mere antonym. A sympathetic reader would view this simply as denoting how immigration researchers acknowledge that the process of settlement has no end-state; that it is a continuous process for the individual to attain further integration (Spencer and Charsley, 2021).

But we find that the lack of end state does not give a free reign to indefinitely problematize structural integrated individuals on the basis of their migrant past. Doing so moves the gaze away from the more evident fact that contemporary society in itself seems far from structurally integrated given the systemic occurrences of discrimination, hostility, and structural inequality that give rise to forms of exclusion and animosity.

To take our reasoning a step further, that individuals cannot be disintegrated denotes that they can neither be integrated to begin with. This internal partitioning of integration as being integrated or paradoxical is thus charged with the task of providing conceptual clarity to a series of ‘mechanisms’ to a concept without an evident antonym. The integration paradox then also denotes an internally propped up semantic framing, or preference, even for a sociopolitical view on migrants that conjures up objectionable problematizations. It can be said there exists a semantic concoction at the heart of the integration paradox which sets migrant behaviour up as contradictory by way of its unidirectional framing.

Indeed, if structural integration is portrayed as a one-sided affair, then the existence of a behavioral paradox is automatically produced by the semantic preferences that researchers operationalize to understand migrants. Ten Teije et al. show the clearest example of this as they state that “there are reasons to expect that the integration paradox is not limited to attitudes toward the native population, but also involves behaviour” (ten Teije et al., 2013, p. 287).

If the term ‘paradox’ is meant here the intuitive response to discrimination, then it would be difficult to find it. This framing of the paradox turns our gaze away from understanding the complex daily contradictions immigrants work with, problematizes it in objectionable ways, and sets out to resolve a non-existent problem of what Green calls an ‘essential ambiguity of the social’ where no resolution is needed nor fruitful (Green, 2019). We can therefore surmise that the integration paradox is an artefact of unsound theory selection practices.

Making the case for cruel optimism

We now know that although empirical studies on the integration paradox vary in empirical outcome measures, we find a tacit consensus that (1) the aspiration of researchers towards attaining an imagined society leads to a one-way solution and therefore fails to attend to various political, social and economic troubles of host societies, (2) semantically props up the concepts in the search for a behavioural paradox, while we are dealing with an artefact of theory selection, conflation with political aims and simplistic measuring instruments, and (3) such practices result in the problematization of individuals and turns the gaze away from the complex affective strategies deployed by immigrants in order to deal with a contradictory existence. Given these three points, it becomes possible to define what parts of the relation between individual settlers and society is captured by a concept such as the integration paradox.

It is often implied that belonging leads to more acceptance. Earning your ‘acceptance’, part of the goal, concerns a normative judgement of approval by the receiving society (de Vroome, 2013; van Doorn et al., 2013). However, by doing away with a homogenous perspective of the native society, and the idea that immigrants must earn all social capital, one can see that belonging does not automatically lead to being accepted *or* becoming accepting. For example, natives can still not accept people who feel like they belong, or settlers and migrants might still feel like they belong but not accept the native population (as research has shown). It is very possible, then, that the thing that migrants desire (to belong and either be accepted or accept) might be an obstacle to their flourishing as citizens, for they could face discrimination, unequal job opportunities, and so on.

These are important observations to make. Because now that we can view the integration paradox as an artefact of unsound theorization, we can tease out *how* problematizations are *imposed* upon the migrant experience rather than *describing* the migrant experience. It is this imposed aspect that makes the integration paradox a case of cruel optimism (Berlant, 2011). As a result, research on this phenomenon superimposed an implicit goal for migrant flourishing that is an obstacle to that very flourishing. For an immigrant to attain something akin to positive emotions and be deemed as a successful case of structural integration, the individual must seem to attach him or herself to social practices that actively impede the aim that brought them here initially. This also means participating in exclusionary and inclusionary practices (Eijberts and Ghorashi, 2017). This concluding remark is in parallel with Pozzo and Nerghes’ research on language acquisition and social integration in contemporary policy programs. The authors found that young refugees find themselves in an “aporia, an unresolvable paradox, because” whether they learn the language or not, “the current policies provide no other path for establishing themselves in the Netherlands” (Pozzo and Nerghes, 2020).

Yet because of this relation of cruel optimism, it is possible to then think about the building blocks of a forward-looking theoretical approach that should do justice to both the psychological *and* social complexity of paradoxes both within and outside the psyche of the individual. For it appears that the current research simplifies not only society, but a wide range of possible affective responses held by individuals.

The grip of poor theorizing and unspoken assumptions seems less burgeoning in the studies of in the papers of Eijberts, Ghorashi, Pozzo and Nerghes. It is no surprise that of this body of knowledge, two studies that came to the fore with conceptual and methodological innovations different from all the papers on the integration paradox discussed so far used an almost

entirely different set of assumptions resulting in a much more subtle and refined view of the integration paradox, much less problematizing the individual rather than policies.

Conclusion

The problem of restricted theorizing with respect to the integration paradox leads to a set of internal contradictions, a co-production of political discourse, and an implicit reinforcement of views on integration that are incongruent with what we know about how we conceptualize integration in general.

We found that researchers conceptualize affective differences as socio-political differences and inscribe it into a simplification of a broad range of integration strategies, that simplification equates good emotions as positive and bad emotions as negative. This functionalist perspective leaves the question as to how we can better distinguish the complex of paradoxes inherent to a settler's behaviour and distinguishing between paradoxes of social behaviour and paradoxes of theory, unanswered. We have provided critical perspective on what the integration paradox aims to explain, and once we consider it as a product of restricted theorizing by scientists, the paradox seems much less a paradox and more a potential case of cruel optimism.

Analytical concepts used in the integration paradox literature are most effectively employed empirically when their theoretical and methodological underpinnings, and the nature of their epistemic and non-epistemic purposes, are fully understood. The time may be ripe, therefore, to renew or reframe the concept of the integration paradox in a way that responds to criticisms.

It would make little sense to use the integrated paradox as a motivation for academic research, especially if the goal is to turn away from the classical assimilation theories towards more contextual and 'multi-layered' understandings of lives replete with paradoxes and contradictions, unless multi-layered means obscuring a few layers as a heuristic practice, which would also be a valid perspective. But then it is not to deny that such heuristic practices then involve a tension: between practicing non-assimilationist research and disavowing some of its core assumptions regarding unidirectional individual-society relations.

We suggest it is especially important to reflect how we, as researchers, (co-)produce objectionable categorizations through the ways we select and test theories if we meagrely explicate what our theories can and cannot not explain. Investigations into a broader range of affective attributes of citizenship and the public sphere could provide a much richer account of how feelings work in proximity of upward mobility, job security, political and social equality, and intimacy. In doing so, researchers will be better equipped to face the complexities of immigrant affect and behaviour and unearth more cogent paradoxes than the integration paradox.

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